

A CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF E-EXAMINATION SYSTEM ACCEPTANCE BY NIGERIAN CIVIL SERVANTS USING UNIFIED THEORY OF ACCEPTANCE AND USE OF TECHNOLOGY (UTAUT) WITH MODERATING EFFECTS OF USER TRAINING AND QUESTIONS CONTENT

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Abstract

E-examination is a system that involves the conduction of examinations using various electronic devices (mobile phones, computers etc) connected to the testing system via the Internet or the Intranet. With increase in the number of civil servants in Kano state Nigeria amounting to 155,186 (one of the highest in Nigeria) manual promotional examination delay the promotion procedures due to manual assessment, recording and processing. E-examination is introduced to curtail this problem and with the objective of eradicating all forms of examination malpractices and promote the use of electronic testing in Nigeria. This study attempts to put forward a conceptual model of UTAUT modification with user training and questions content as moderating variables towards user acceptance of this innovation. The study's approach is based on literature review on the basis that, the incorporation of these variables into UTAUT model in context of E-examination demand attention. The variables are proposed as antecedents of this useful tool of e-examination.

Consequently, the proposed model is set forward as the basis for future empirical study in this area. UTAUT model/theory was formed through the incorporation of eight famous model/theories in the diverse field and the idea was to arrive at a unified view of user acceptance of IT. Empirical results of the UTAUT model revealed it was able to account for 70% of variance in usage intention. This result to a large extent does better than that of any of the original eight models/theories and their extensions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Being the most populous state in Nigeria, Kano is one of the states with the highest number of civil servants. Presently Kano state has 155, 186 (One hundred and fifty-five thousand one hundred and eighty-six) civil servants under its payroll who are permanent and pensionable [1]. Before the introduction of this electronic examination all promotional and other civil service examinations (Like change of cadre exam, clerical examinations) are done manually using traditional paper-pencil method. Due to

the increasing number of personnel, and incessant complains about delay in releasing promotional examination results, missing examination scripts, and impersonations, the office of the head of service introduced an electronic examination system to curtail these problems and past track promotion procedures. The electronic examination began from January 2016 as a pilot program for its senior officers (Grade level 07 to above) and with a plan of full implementation of all civil service examinations as computer-based by January 2019 [1]. The E-examination system design is simple. The login page needs the staff surname as the username while personal subhead number (PSN) is used as password. If the information entered are correct a page will open with the staff full name and picture and some vital information about his career like current level, next expected level, remaining years in service and expected day of retirement. The examinee had to push “next button” to take him to next page. On this page the examinee must choose one of the three segments of questions namely: General Knowledge, Civil service knowledge and professional knowledge. On Each segment each page had the question, the four possible answers and the “next” button. The examinee had only to choose the right answer and then he/she had to push the “next” button. The text is in English. So, invigilators did not give any other special instruction during the examination. They only helped examinees that were not very comfortable with the use of computer and they asked information on how to operate. The E-examination system was built in a Windows XP machine using JavaScript with Perl CGI on Apache web server with MySQL. The effective development of an E-examination system depends on students’ acceptance [2]. Figure 1 shows the architectural design of the E-examination system.

Figure 1: E- Examination system Architecture

Understanding the conditions under which Information Technology is accepted and used remains one of the most prominent issues in information system research.

Despite its intended success and applause by the civil servants, introducing an innovation like this will not lack challenges of adoption and acceptability by the subjects concerned. Based on preliminary study carried out by the researchers some civil servants complained of ill timing of the innovation due to the level of computer literacy among the generality of the civil servants. So, the objective of this study is to conceptually modified UTAUT to serve as a useful tool for government to predict the likelihood of successful acceptance of this new technology introduced and help them understand the drivers of user acceptance.

2 PROPOSED WORK

The constructs of UTAUT model are performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and facilitating conditions [3], including anxiety that was established not to have a positive relation with behavioral intention. The proposed moderating variables are user training and questions content which are entirely positing to have a significant role on moderating performance expectancy and effort expectancy that are direct determinants of behavioral intention toward user acceptance of E-examination system. Also Moderated by age, gender and experience, [3] in their analysis of

eight models/theories of technology acceptance, found that with the exception of Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) and Motivational Model (MM), the predictive validity of the models increased after including the moderating variable. Figure 2 shows the conceptual framework of the model.

Figure 2: A Conceptual Model of UTAUT modification in the context of E-Examination.

The variables indicated in the conceptual model are thus defined based on ([3]; [7]; [8]).

The conceptual model is constructed to answer the following research questions:

- (1) What are the drivers for user acceptance of E-examination for promotion by Kano state civil servants.
- (2) Do the variables such as gender, age, computer experience make a difference?
- (3) What impact do the variables user-training and questions content have on users' behavioral intention?

3 CONCLUSIONS

The study merely proposes a conceptual model for measuring acceptability in context of E-examination system for Nigerian civil servants. The research presented is limited being that, the proposed model is only based on literature review. Subsequent researches should focus on empirical validation of the conceptual model using instruments.

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